

Calculation of **Percentage Depth Dose (PDD)** by using different Ionizing Radiations

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BS Project Report

In

BS Physics

COMSATS University Islamabad,
Lahore Campus- Pakistan

(Spring 2023)

COMSATS University Islamabad

Calculation of Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) by using different ionizing beams

A Project Report Presented to

COMSATS University Islamabad, Lahore Campus

In partial fulfillment

The requirement for the degree of

BS (Physics)

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(Spring 2023)

Project Report Title

An Undergraduate project report submitted to the Department of Physics as partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of Degree of BS (Physics)

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DEDICATIONS

First, we are grateful to ALLAH and we would dedicate this work to our parents. After this with our deepest gratitude and warmest affection we dedicate this thesis to **Dr. Naima Amin**. Without their courageous inspiration and intellectual guidance, we were not able to proceed with research. Then, Directorial teachers, who have been a constant source of knowledge and inspiration and all supporting friends.

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

In The Name Of ALLAH, The Most Gracious, The Most Merciful

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All praises to **Allah Almighty**, who provided me with the strength to accomplish the final year project (FYP). All respect for his **Holy Prophet (PBUH)**, whose teachings are the resources of knowledge & guidance for whole mankind.

Before anybody else, I thank my parents, who have always been a source of moral support and a driving force behind whatever I do. I am indebted to my project advisor **Dr. Naima Amin** for her encouragement, inspiring guidance, remarkable suggestions, constructive criticism & friendly discussions which enabled us to complete this report. Without her kind patronization, sincere coaching and continuous consultation, I would not have been able to complete this successfully fully.

Heartily, I am thankful to **Dr. Naima Amin** for her constant and selfless support at every stage of project work.

I am also grateful to **Dr. Muhamad Asif HOD** of the physics department at CUI Lahore. His encouraging behavior as well as support at really opened new windows of knowledge for me. I offer my deepest appreciation to him for providing me with the lab/research facilities.

The **ideas** of report/thesis writing are usually attributable to all sources, which helped me a lot to compile it. This is all due to the illuminated guidance of our teachers as they are the builders of my academic carrier, all this could not have been done without their enlightened supervision and coaching.

I am also thankful to the librarian at COMSATS library.

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NOMENCLATURES

- **PDD:** Percentage Depth Dose
- **SSD:** Source to surface distance
- **DNA:** Deoxyribonucleic acid
- **LINAC:** Linear Accelerator
- **LQM:** Linear Quadratic Model
- **SKMCH&RC:** Shaukat Khanum Memorial Cancer Hospital & Research Centre
- **OARs:** Organs at risk
- **EBRT:** External Beam Radiotherapy
- **IR:** Ionizing Radiations
- **SIB-IMRT:** Simultaneously Integrated Boost Intensity Modulated Radiation Therapy
- **BED:** Biological Effective Dose
- **EQD2:** Biological Equivalent Dose for 2 Gy Fraction
- **PTV:** Planning Target Volume
- **eLQ:** Equivalent Dose Calculator
- **RT:** Radiation Therapy
- **MRI:** Magnetic Resonance Image
- **DDM:** Depth of Dose maximum

Chapter # 01

INTRODUCTION

1.1 What is Cancer?

Cancer is a disease in which some of the body's cells grow uncontrollably and spread to other parts of the body.

Cancer can start almost anywhere in the human body, which is made up of trillions of cells. Normally, human cells grow and multiply (through a process called cell division) to form new cells as the body needs them. When cells grow old or become damaged, they die, and new cells take their place.

Cancer remains one of the top destroyers of life. Shortly, with the universal growth of the world's population and continuing changes in lifestyle in the population of large developing countries, the global rate of cancer is expected to increase, rather than decrease [1].

1.2 Difference between Cancer Cells and Normal Cell

Cancer cells differ from normal cells in many ways. For instance:

- Cancer cells grow in the absence of signals telling them to grow. Normal cells only grow when they receive such signals.
- These cells ignore signals that normally tell cells to stop dividing or to die (a process is known as Programmed cell death or apoptosis).
- These cells invade nearby areas and spread to other areas of the body. Normal cells stop growing when they encounter other cells, and most normal cells do not move around the body.
- These cells tell blood vessels to grow toward tumors.

These blood vessels supply tumors with oxygen and nutrients and remove waste products from tumors.

Normal cells can usually repair themselves faster and maintain their normal function status than cancer cells. Radiation aims to provide the maximum dose to aberrant cancer cells while minimizing the impact on healthy cells [3].

Figure 2 Difference between Cancer Cells and Normal Cell [2]

1.3 How Does Cancer Develop?

Cancer develops in cells, which are the body's building blocks. According to biological studies, the body creates new cells as needed and replaces old ones. Cancer is a disease in which certain cells in the body grow uncontrollably and spread to other parts of the body.

Cancer is a term that refers to a group of diseases rather than a single disease. There are at least 100 different forms of cancer. Most cancer names are derived from the location where it first occurs. Lung cancer, for example, appears in the lung, while breast cancer appears in the breast. The spread of malignant cells from one part of the body to another is referred to as metastasis. Cancerous cells may appear in one location and then spread through the lymph nodes. These are immune cell clusters found throughout the body.

Figure 2: Cancer Development Process [4]

Cancer is a genetic disease that is, it is caused by changes to genes that control the way our cells function, especially how they grow and divide.

Genetic changes that cause cancer can happen because of:

- Errors that occur as cells divide.
- DNA damage caused by harmful substances in the environment, such as the chemicals in tobacco smoke and ultraviolet rays from the sun. (Our Cancer Causes and Prevention section has more information.)
- They were inherited from our parents.

The body normally eliminates cells with damaged DNA before they turn cancerous. But the body's ability to do so goes down as we age. This is part of the reason why there is a higher risk of cancer later in life.

Each person's cancer has a unique combination of genetic changes. As the cancer continues to grow, additional changes will occur. Even within the same tumor, different cells may have different genetic changes.

Figure 3: Cancer is caused by certain changes to genes [5].

Cancer that has spread from the place where it first formed to another place in the body is called metastatic cancer. The process by which cancer cells spread to other parts of the body is called metastasis. Metastatic cancer has the same name and type of cancer cells as the original or primary cancer. For example, breast cancer that forms a metastatic tumor in the lung is metastatic, not lung cancer.

There are more than 100 types of cancer. Types of cancer are usually named for the organs or tissues where the cancers form. For example, lung cancer starts in the lung, and brain cancer starts in the brain. Cancers also may be described by the type of cell that formed them, such as an epithelial or squamous cell [6].

1.4 How Ionizing Beams Interact with Cancer Cells?

Radiation is energy that's carried by waves or a stream of particles. Radiation works by damaging the genes (DNA) in cells. Genes control how cells grow and divide. When radiation damages the genes of cancer cells, they can't grow and divide any more.

When ionizing radiation beams are directed toward cancer cells during radiation therapy, they interact with these cells in several ways. Ionizing radiation refers to radiation with enough energy to remove tightly bound electrons from atoms, leading to the formation of charged particles called ions. These ions can cause damage to the DNA within cells, ultimately preventing cancer cells from reproducing and leading to their destruction [7].

Direct-type damage results from radiation energy being deposited directly into the DNA, whereas indirect damage occurs when the species created by the interaction of the primary radiation and SEs within the molecular environment surrounding the DNA (e.g., salts, proteins, oxygen, and water) react with the molecule.

Here's a closer look at how ionizing radiation interacts with cancer cells:

1.4.1 Direct DNA Damage: Ionizing radiation can directly damage the DNA molecules within cancer cells. When radiation passes through the cell, it can break the chemical bonds that hold the DNA together, causing structural damage to the DNA strands. This damage can disrupt the cell's ability to replicate and divide, leading to cell death.

1.4.2 Indirect DNA Damage: Ionizing radiation can also indirectly damage the DNA within cancer cells. As the radiation passes through the cells, it can ionize water molecules within the cell, producing highly reactive free radicals. These free radicals can then react with nearby DNA molecules, causing chemical changes and DNA damage. The damaged DNA disrupts the cell's normal functions and can eventually lead to cell death [9].

Figure 4: Direct & Indirect DNA damage [8]

Radiation therapy plays a vital role in the comprehensive treatment of cancer. Its ability to precisely target and destroy cancer cells offers patients a chance at remission or symptom relief, improving their quality of life. Before undergoing radiation therapy, a patient typically goes through a planning process known as simulation. During simulation, imaging techniques like CT scans or MRI scans are used to determine the exact location, size, and shape of the tumor. This information helps the radiation oncologist create a personalized treatment plan, ensuring the radiation is accurately directed to the tumor while minimizing damage to surrounding healthy tissues. Radiation therapy is usually delivered in multiple sessions called fractions. Each fraction consists of a specific dose of radiation, and the total number of fractions varies depending on the type, stage, and location of the cancer. Treatment schedules can span over a few weeks or months, with regular sessions scheduled to allow healthy cells time to recover while continuing to attack cancer cells.

With ongoing research and advancements, radiation therapy continues to evolve, ensuring more effective and personalized treatment options for cancer patients. Along with surgery and chemotherapy, RT plays a vital role in cancer treatment.

Radiotherapy intends to maximize the prescribed dose for abnormal cancer cells and minimize the effect on healthy cells [10].

1.5 Ionizing Radiation

Ionizing radiation refers to radiation that carries enough energy to remove tightly bound electrons from atoms, resulting in the creation of ions. (OR)

The energy emitted from a source is generally referred to as radiation. Examples include heat or light from the sun, microwaves from an oven, X-rays from an X-ray tube, and gamma rays from radioactive elements. Ionizing radiation can remove electrons from the atoms, i.e. it can ionize atoms.

Radiation has been described as a “two-edged sword” because it is a major approach to cancer treatment, and it can also cause cancer [11]. High-energy photons damage the DNA. They stop their ability to divide and proliferate further. Radiations directly or indirectly damage both normal and cancerous cells. Normal/ healthy cells can repair themselves rapidly. While tumor cells are not good at repairing as healthy/normal cells in repairing the damage that is caused by radiotherapy.

Ionizing beams are streams of particles that possess sufficient energy to ionize atoms and molecules by removing electrons from them.

Figure 5 Types of Radiation beams [12]

Types of ionizing Radiations are;

- 1.5.1 Electron beams
- 1.5.2 Proton beams
- 1.5.3 Neutron beams &
- 1.5.4 Photon beam

1.5.1 Electron Beam: An electron beam consists of high-energy electrons. Electron beams are commonly used in various applications, including medical radiation therapy, industrial material processing, and electron microscopy. They can penetrate a few centimeters into materials, depending on their energy, and cause ionization by colliding with atoms and transferring energy to them.

1.5.2 Proton Beam: A proton beam is composed of high-energy protons. Proton beams are utilized in proton therapy, a specialized form of radiation therapy for cancer treatment. Protons can penetrate tissues to specific depths, delivering their maximum energy near the end of their range, which allows for precise targeting of tumors while sparing surrounding healthy tissues.

1.5.3 Neutron Beam: A neutron beam consists of high-energy neutrons. Neutrons are electrically neutral particles found in atomic nuclei. Neutron beams are primarily employed in scientific research, material analysis, and neutron therapy. Neutrons have unique properties and interact differently with matter compared to electrons and protons. They are highly penetrating and can cause ionization through nuclear reactions, scattering, and other processes [13-16].

Figure 6 : Skin Cancer [17]

1.5.4 Photon Beam: A type of radiation therapy that uses x-rays or gamma rays that come from a special machine called a linear accelerator. The radiation dose is delivered at the surface of the body and goes into the tumor and through the body. Photon beam radiation therapy is different from proton beam therapy.

1.6 Dosimetry:

Dosimetry is the measurement and calculation of the amount of radiation that is absorbed by an object or person [18].

1.7 How Dosimetry relates to Ionizing Beams?

In radiation therapy, dosimetry is essential for delivering the prescribed radiation dose to cancerous tumors while minimizing the dose to surrounding healthy tissues. The accurate measurement and calculation of the radiation dose are critical to achieving the desired therapeutic outcome and avoiding excessive radiation damage.

Ionizing radiation interacts with cancer cells and deposits their energy and kills the cancerous tissues [19-20].

1.8 Precision in Dosimetry:

Precision in dosimetry refers to the accuracy and precision of the measurements of radiation dose delivered on the tumor. In radiation therapy, precise and accurate dosimetry is critical to ensure that the desired dose is delivered to the target volume while minimizing the dose to surrounding healthy tissues [21].

In the context of dosimetry, precision is a measure of the consistency and repeatability of dose measurements or calculations. It indicates the ability to obtain similar results when measurements are repeated under the same conditions. High precision is desirable in dosimetry because it ensures that radiation doses are accurately determined, leading to effective and safe radiation treatments or practices.

Several factors contribute to achieving precision in dosimetry:

1.8.1 Calibration: Accurate calibration of radiation measurement devices, such as ionization chambers or dosimeters, is crucial. Calibration involves establishing a known relationship between the measured response of the device and the actual radiation dose.

1.8.2 Quality Assurance: Regular quality assurance procedures help identify and correct any uncertainties or errors in the dosimetry process. This includes checks on equipment performance, calibration verification, and adherence to established protocols and standards.

1.8.3 Standardization: Following established protocols and standards ensures consistency in dosimetry practices across different facilities and institutions. Standardization allows for reliable comparisons of dose measurements and calculations.

1.8.4 Dosimetry Systems and Algorithms: Utilizing advanced dosimetry systems and algorithms, such as treatment planning systems, can contribute to improved precision. These systems incorporate sophisticated mathematical models and algorithms that calculate dose distributions based on patient-specific data.

1.8.5 Training and Expertise: Well-trained personnel with expertise in dosimetry are essential for achieving precision. They should be knowledgeable about the equipment, measurement techniques, and the underlying physics of radiation interactions [22-23].

1.9 Consequences of Non-Precise Dosimetry:

Non-precision in dosimetry can have significant consequences in various fields, particularly those involving radiation therapy, industrial radiography, and radiation safety.

Here are some potential consequences:

1.9.1 Inaccurate Radiation Doses: Dosimetry is crucial for ensuring that the desired amount of radiation is delivered to a specific target area, such as a tumor during radiation therapy.

Non-precision in dosimetry can lead to inaccurate measurements and calculations, resulting in the delivery of either insufficient or excessive radiation doses. Insufficient doses may fail to effectively treat the target, while excessive doses can harm healthy tissues and organs [24].

1.9.2 Reduced Treatment Efficacy: Precision in dosimetry is essential to optimize the effectiveness of radiation therapy. Inadequate doses may fail to eliminate the tumor or control its growth, potentially leading to disease recurrence. Conversely, excessive doses can cause severe damage to healthy tissues, compromising their ability to recover and increasing the risk of complications.

1.9.3 Increased Risk to Patients: Non-precision in dosimetry can expose patients to unnecessary risks. In radiation therapy, precise dosimetry is vital to minimize the radiation dose to healthy tissues and organs surrounding the target area. Inaccurate measurements and calculations can result in unintended exposure to radiation, leading to short-term and long-term side effects, such as radiation-induced organ dysfunction (abnormal functioning of an organ), secondary malignancies, and other radiation-related complications [25-26].

A **secondary malignancy** is new cancer that occurs in an individual as a result of previous treatment with radiation or chemotherapy. Secondary cancers may occur months or years after treatment and are a consequence or side effect of the initial cancer treatment.

1.9.4 Occupational Hazards: In industrial radiography, non-precision in dosimetry can pose risks to radiation workers. Dosimeters are used to monitor the radiation exposure of personnel working with radioactive materials or radiation-emitting equipment. If dosimeters provide inaccurate readings, it can lead to underestimation or overestimation of radiation exposure, potentially compromising the safety of workers. This can result in excessive radiation doses, leading to acute radiation sickness, long-term health effects, or increased risks of radiation-related diseases.

1.9.5 Regulatory Compliance and Legal Consequences: Precision in dosimetry is essential to comply with regulatory requirements and standards. Inaccurate dosimetry practices can lead to violations of safety regulations and guidelines, potentially resulting in legal consequences for individuals or organizations involved. Regulatory bodies closely monitor radiation-related practices, and non-compliance due to non-precision in dosimetry can result in penalties, fines, legal actions, and reputational damage [27-29].

Figure 7: In metastasis, cancer cells break away from where they first formed and form new tumors in other parts of the body [30]

1.9.6 Lack of Confidence in Radiation Practices: Non-precision in dosimetry can undermine confidence in radiation practices, both among healthcare professionals and the general public. Accurate dosimetry is crucial to ensure the safe and effective use of radiation for medical purposes. If dosimetry errors occur frequently or are not promptly addressed, it can erode trust in radiation therapy as a treatment modality. This lack of confidence may lead to reluctance among patients to undergo necessary treatments or result in delays in seeking appropriate medical care [31].

Chapter # 2

MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Methods to Calculate the Radiation Dose:

There are the following Methods to Calculate the Radiation dose,

2.1.1 Percentage Depth Dose (PDD)

2.1.2 Tissue Air Ratio (TAR)

2.1.3 Tissue Maximum Ratio (TMR)

2.1.4 Tissue Phantom Ratio (TPR)

2.2 Percentage Depth Dose:

Percentage depth dose (PDD) is a term used in radiation therapy to describe the dose distribution of a radiation beam as it penetrates the patient's body. It represents the percentage of the maximum dose delivered by the beam at a specific depth in the patient's tissue.

It is a measure of the percentage of radiation dose delivered by a beam of ionizing radiation at different depths in tissue, relative to the dose delivered at a reference depth, which is usually taken as the maximum dose depth.

$$P = D_o/D_{max} *100$$

PDD data is commonly used in treatment planning to determine the dose delivered to a specific depth in the patient's body. It helps in optimizing treatment techniques and calculating appropriate treatment parameters to ensure that the prescribed dose is accurately delivered to the target volume while minimizing the dose to surrounding healthy tissues.

2.2.1 Parameters of PDD:

PDD varies with depth, beam energy, field size, and source-to-surface distance (SSD).

The percentage depth dose (beyond the depth of the maximum dose) increases with beam energy. Higher-energy beams have greater penetrating power and thus deliver a higher-percentage depth dose.

PDD decreases with increasing depth due to the inverse square law and due to attenuation of the radiation beam.

The PDD curve provides important information about the dose deposition characteristics of the radiation beam. It demonstrates how the dose decreases as the beam travels deeper into the tissue. The shape of the curve is influenced by factors such as beam energy, field size, and tissue composition. Different radiation beam modalities, such as a photon or electron beams, will have different PDD characteristics.

2.3 Tissue Air Ratio:

Tissue-air ratio (TAR) was first introduced by Johns in 1953 and was originally called the “tumor-air ratio.” At that time, this quantity was intended specifically for rotation therapy calculations. In rotation therapy, the radiation source moves in a circle around the axis of rotation, which is usually placed in the tumor.

Tissue Air Ratio (TAR) is the ratio of the absorbed dose at a given depth in tissue to the absorbed dose at the same point in air.

2.4 Tissue Phantom Ratio:

The TPR is defined as the ratio of the dose at a given point in phantom to the dose at the same point at a fixed reference depth, usually 5 cm.

2.5 Tissue maximum ratio:

The TAR was defined for low X-ray energies at a time when high energy beams were rare. The TMR is a variation of the TAR that makes it suitable for use at high energies.

TMR is a special case of TPR and may be defined as the ratio of the dose at a given point in phantom to the dose at the same point at the reference depth of maximum dose [32-33].

2.4 Linear accelerator (LINAC)

A linear accelerator (LINAC) is a machine that delivers high-energy X-rays or electrons to the region of a patient's tumor [34].

It is commonly used for external beam radiation treatments for patients with cancer. The LINAC customizes high energy x-rays or electrons to conform to a tumor's shape and destroy cancer cells while sparing surrounding normal tissue

The LINAC is programmed before each session to deliver high-energy X-rays that conform to the specific size, shape, and location of a tumor.

This way, the LINAC can target and destroy cancerous cells in a precise area of a patient's body with minimal exposure to the surrounding healthy tissue. LINACs help cancer specialists treat cancers of the brain, spine, head and neck, lung, breast, esophagus, stomach, rectum, uterus, prostate, bladder, liver, and bones

The LINAC features several built-in safety measures to ensure that it will deliver the dose as prescribed and is routinely checked by medical physicists to make sure that each treatment is delivered in the same manner [35].

The linear accelerator, often known as a LINAC, is sophisticated radiotherapy treatment equipment. The electron beam is accelerated in an accelerator using microwave technology similar to that used in radar. The beam is directed to the target via a waveguide. They collide with a metal target and produce high-energy X-rays as a result.

Radiotherapy has continued to improve thanks to a combination of new procedures and attention to how patients are best set up and treated. Many treatments such as conformal radiotherapy (3D-CRT, 2D-CRT), intensity modulated radiation therapy (IMRT), external beam radiotherapy (EBRT), and brachytherapy are available in this linear accelerator [36].

The linear accelerator uses microwave technology (similar to that used for radar) to accelerate electrons in a part of the accelerator called the "wave guide," which then allows these electrons to collide with a heavy metal target to produce high-energy x-rays. These high-energy X-rays are shaped as they exit the machine to conform to the shape of the patient's tumor and the customized beam is directed to the patient's tumor. The beam is usually shaped by a multi-leaf collimator that is incorporated into the head of the machine. The patient lies on a moveable treatment couch and lasers are used to make sure the patient is in the proper position. The treatment couch can move in many directions including up, down, right, left, in, and out. The beam comes out of a part of the accelerator called a gantry, which can be rotated around the patient. Radiation can be delivered to the tumor from many angles by rotating the gantry and moving the treatment couch [37].

2.5 Intensity Modulated Radiation Technique (IMRT):

Intensity-modulated radiation therapy (IMRT) is a type of external beam radiation therapy (EBRT) that uses computer-controlled intensity modulation to precisely deliver radiation to a tumor while minimizing the dose to surrounding healthy tissue. IMRT is used to treat a variety of cancers, including head and neck cancers, lung cancer, prostate cancer, and brain tumors.

IMRT works by using a linear accelerator (LINAC) to generate beams of high-energy X-rays. The LINAC can be moved in three dimensions, and the intensity of the X-ray beams can be varied. This allows the radiation oncologist to create a radiation dose distribution that conforms to the shape of the tumor.

IMRT has several advantages over traditional EBRT. It can deliver higher doses of radiation to the tumor while sparing healthy tissue, which can improve the chances of a cure. IMRT can also be used to treat tumors that are located near critical structures, such as the brain or spinal cord, where traditional EBRT would be too risky.

By the principle of IMRT; beams of radiation can be projected from any direction but initially, to distinguish between two separate classes of techniques, only coplanar beam directions will be considered. IMRT technique consists of a series of beam directions each defined by the linear accelerator gantry angle. From each beam direction, a modulated beam is projected towards the isocenter. The beams can be narrow fan beams, modulated in one dimension, or divergent cone beams modulated in two dimensions [38-40].

Figure 8 Sketch of a gantry used in a radiation therapy machine [41]

Moreover in this study SIB- IMRT technique is used to deliver the doses. The simultaneous integrated boost IMRT technique delivers the different dose levels to different target volumes simultaneously within a single treatment fraction [42-43].

Figure 9 Graphical representation of the volumes of interest, as defined by the ICRU 50 and 62 reports.[44]

- 2.5.1 Gross Tumor Volume GTV:** The visible tumor volume that can be felt by hand and can be detected by methods such as CT or MR.
- 2.5.2 Clinical Target Volume:** In various studies, it was shown that there were undetectable subclinical malignant cells around the gross tumor. Thus, it was considered that these areas should also be included in the treatment volume. The treatment volume is determined by the radiation oncologist based on the aim of treatment (cure versus palliation). $CTV = GTV +$ subclinical disease area.
- 2.5.3 Planning Target Volume:** Patient and machine factors are considered in the delineation of the planning target volume (PTV), which is a geometrical definition. Accurate selection of radiation areas and sizes to create the desired dose in CTV depends on the definition of PTV by considering error margins. PTV volume and shape are determined by the selected therapy techniques such as SBRT, tumor location, and set-up errors that depend on the previously defined CTV. In addition, PTV is dependent on tumor location. The required confidence margins should be added to the therapy plan to minimize these problems. Internal margins include physiological alterations in position, volume, and shape of the tumor according to anatomical reference points (i.e. bladder and rectum become full differently in each treatment, respiration, intestine, and heart movements). The set-up margin includes patient-specific clinical and instrument-specific mechanical and dosimetric factors besides the unavailability of the same position for the patient and radiation area according to coordinate systems of therapy instruments [45-46].

$$PTV = CTV + \text{internal margin (IM)} + \text{set-up margin (SM)}$$

2.6 ORGANS at Risk (OARs):

Radiation therapy uses high-energy beams to kill cancer cells. However, the radiation can also damage healthy cells. The more radiation that healthy cells receive, the more likely they are to be damaged.

Organs at risk (OARs) are healthy tissues or organs that are located near a tumor and that could be damaged by radiation therapy [47].

2.7 Linear Quadratic Model:

The linear-quadratic model (LQM) is a mathematical model used to describe the relationship between the dose of ionizing radiation and the probability of cell death. The model is based on the idea that cell death can be caused by either single-strand DNA breaks (SSBs) or double-strand DNA breaks (DSBs). SSBs can be repaired by the cell, but DSBs are usually lethal. The LQM assumes that the probability of a cell dying from a single SSB is proportional to the dose of radiation, while the probability of a cell dying from a DSB is proportional to the square of the dose [48].

The LQM can be used to calculate the dose required to kill a certain fraction of cells, known as the 'dose-response curve'. The dose-response curve is typically sigmoidal in shape, with a steep initial slope and a shallower slope at higher doses. The steep initial slope is caused by the linear component of the LQM, while the shallower slope is caused by the quadratic component.

Figure 10 *Illustration of LQ curves: Responses for cell lines with high and low α/β ratios* [49]

The LQM has been used to great success in predicting the effects of radiation on cells in vitro. However, its applicability to in vivo studies is less clear. This is because the LQM does not take into account the effects of repair mechanisms, which are more important in vivo than in vitro.

Despite its limitations, the LQM is a valuable tool for understanding the effects of radiation on cells. It has been used to develop new cancer treatments, such as radiation therapy [50].

Here is the mathematical formula for the LQM:

$$S = e^{-\alpha d - \beta d^2}$$

Where:

- S is the fraction of cells surviving
- d is the dose to which it is exposed
- α is the linear coefficient
- β is the quadratic coefficient

The α/β ratio is a measure of the relative importance of the linear and quadratic components of the LQM. Cells with a high α/β ratio are more sensitive to radiation, while cells with a low α/β ratio are less sensitive [51].

The LQ model showed therapeutic utility in estimating the effect of fractionated radiation on healthy cells and comparing the equivalent total dosage of various fractionation plans. The estimation of radiotherapeutic outcome is dependent on the accuracy of the LQ parameters, α , β , and α/β .

Reactions	α/β values
1- Early Reactions	
Skin	9-12
Jejunum	6-10
Colon	10-11
Testis	12-13
2- Late Reactions	
Spinal cord, Brain	1.8-2.2
Kidney	2-2.4
Rectum	2.5-5
Lung	2.7-4
Bladder	3-7

Table 1: Ratios of alpha beta for early and late radiation reactions in normal tissues, determined from clinical data.

If the α/β ratio is high (e.g. 10 Gy) for a clone of cancer cell/ tumor removal/killing, but low (e.g. 3 Gy) for late normal tissue complications, then delivering external beam radiotherapy in a large number (20-30) of small (≈ 2 Gy) dose fractions should yield the highest ‘therapeutic ratio’; this is demonstrated via the linear-quadratic model of cell killing. Thus α/β ratio is the measure of how soon the survival curve begins to bend over significantly [52].

In addition; the LQ model is a mechanistic biologically based model. It has well-documented predictive properties for dose rate effects in the laboratory.

2.8 Biological Effective Dose:

BED is a measure of the true biological dose delivered by a particular combination of dose per fraction and total dose to a particular tissue characterized by a specific α/β ratio”. When ionizing radiation interacts with a determined volume of living tissue, this can or cannot interact with all cells, can or cannot produce effects as a result of their interactions; and the first fraction of a fractionated treatment produces a partial number of killed and sub lethally damaged cells from the total initially undamaged ones. During the second and successive fractions, the radiation can interact with these three kinds of cells, where the interactions can produce the same effects as the first fraction from the undamaged cells and SLDCs.

BED has a direct relationship with the radiation biological effects, in particular the cell survival (S) in radiation treatments with n fractions, d dose per fractions delivered in tissues characterized with LQ parameters α and α/β . The BED expression was a result of a mathematical derivation of the exponential part of the LQ S model for treatments with n fractions and dose per fraction d, where $D = nd$; and this model was obtained assuming that all sub-lethally damaged cells are wholly repaired during the intrafraction period.

$$BED = nd[1+d/\alpha/\beta]$$

Where “n” is the number of fractions and “d” is the dose per fraction. “D” is the total dose and “ $1+d/\alpha/\beta$ ” is the relative effectiveness. BED represents the physical dose required for a given effect if the dose were to be delivered by infinitely small doses per fraction or, in the case of continuous radiation rates, at a very low dose rate.

2.9 Equivalent Dose:

It is calculated for different organs. It is based on the absorbed dose to an organ, adjusted to account for the effectiveness of the type of radiation. It is expressed in millisieverts (mSv) to an organ. The SI unit of measure for an equivalent dose is the Sievert, defined as one Joule per kg. Equivalent dose H_T is used for assessing stochastic health risks (probabilistic effects that occur by chance) due to external radiation fields that penetrate uniformly through the whole body. However,

it needs further corrections when the field is applied only to part(s) of the body, or non-uniformly to measure the overall stochastic health risk to the body. To enable this a further dose quantity called effective dose must be used to take into account the varying sensitivity of different organs and tissues to radiation. Whilst an equivalent dose is used for the stochastic effects of external radiation, a similar approach is used for internal, or committed doses. The ICRP defines an equivalent dose quantity for an individual committed dose, which is used to measure the effect of inhaled or ingested radioactive materials. A committed dose from an internal source represents the same effective risk as the same amount of equivalent dose applied uniformly to the whole body from an external source.

The equivalent dose is used to assess how much biological damage is expected from the absorbed dose of a certain type of radiation. Because all radiation used in diagnostic medicine has the same low-harm potential, the equivalent dose in Sv is numerically equal to the absorbed dose in Gy [53].

$$EQD2 = BED / (1 + 2 \alpha / \beta)$$

CHAPTER #03

RESULT & DISCUSSIONS

Table 2: Depth VS Energies (field size 15*15; SSD=100cm)

Percentage Depth Dose							
SSD 100cm							
Field Size 15*15 cm ²							
Beam Energy	6MeV	9MeV	12MeV	15MeV	18MeV	20MeV	22MeV
Depth(cm)	Dose%						
0	78.2	81.2	86.2	90.7	92.7	92.5	92.2
0.1	79.9	82.2	87.0	91.3	93.3	93.1	92.7
0.2	81.8	83.3	87.9	92.0	94.0	93.8	93.5
0.3	83.9	84.6	88.9	92.9	94.8	94.9	94.6
0.4	86.0	85.7	89.9	93.7	95.7	95.6	95.5
0.5	88.3	86.8	90.6	94.3	96.3	96.3	96.2
0.6	90.5	87.9	91.3	94.9	96.9	96.9	96.7
0.7	92.8	88.9	91.9	95.4	97.3	97.3	97.2
0.8	95.0	90.0	92.5	95.8	97.7	97.7	97.6
0.9	96.9	91.0	92.9	96.1	98.1	98.0	98.0
1	98.4	92.1	93.5	96.5	98.3	98.3	98.3
1.1	99.5	93.1	93.9	96.8	98.5	98.5	98.5
1.2	99.8	94.1	94.3	97.0	98.8	98.8	98.8
1.3	100.0	95.2	94.7	97.3	99.0	98.9	99.0
1.4	99.4	96.2	95.2	97.5	99.1	99.1	99.2
1.5	97.7	97.2	95.7	97.8	99.3	99.3	99.3
1.6	95.1	98.0	96.1	98.0	99.4	99.4	99.5
1.7	91.5	98.8	96.6	98.2	99.5	99.5	99.6
1.8	87.0	99.4	97.0	98.4	99.6	99.6	99.7
1.9	81.7	99.7	97.4	98.6	99.7	99.7	99.8
2	75.4	99.9	97.9	98.8	99.8	99.8	99.8
2.1	69.2	100.0	98.3	98.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
2.2	62.0	99.6	98.6	99.1	99.9	99.9	100.0
2.3	54.3	98.8	99.0	99.3	99.9	100.0	100.0
2.4	46.3	97.5	99.3	99.4	100.0	100.0	100.0
2.5	38.5	95.8	99.6	99.5	100.0	100.0	100.0
2.6	31.0	93.7	99.8	99.6	100.0	100.0	100.0
2.7	23.8	91.0	99.9	99.7	100.0	99.9	100.0
2.8	17.8	88.1	100.0	99.8	100.0	99.9	100.0

2.9	12.8	84.3	99.9	99.9	100.0	99.9	99.9
3	9.0	80.4	99.7	100.0	100.0	99.9	99.8
3.1	5.8	75.7	99.5	100.0	100.0	99.8	99.8
3.2	3.6	71.0	98.9	100.0	99.9	99.7	99.7
3.3	2.2	65.3	98.1	99.9	99.8	99.6	99.6
3.4	1.5	59.8	97.4	99.8	99.7	99.6	99.5
3.5	1.1	53.9	96.3	99.7	99.7	99.5	99.4
3.6	0.9	48.1	94.9	99.6	99.6	99.4	99.2
3.7	0.9	42.2	93.3	99.3	99.5	99.3	99.0
3.8	0.8	36.2	91.5	99.0	99.3	99.1	98.9
3.9	0.8	30.1	89.2	98.6	99.1	99.0	98.8
4	0.8	25.0	86.9	98.1	99.0	98.8	98.7
4.1	0.8	19.8	84.0	97.5	98.8	98.6	98.5
4.2	0.8	15.6	81.3	96.8	98.6	98.5	98.3
4.3	0.8	11.8	78.0	96.0	98.3	98.3	98.1
4.4	0.8	8.7	74.5	95.0	98.0	98.1	97.9
4.5	0.8	6.3	70.4	94.0	97.8	97.8	97.7
4.6	0.8	4.6	66.5	92.8	97.3	97.6	97.4
4.7	0.8	3.4	62.3	91.4	96.8	97.3	97.1
4.8	0.8	2.5	58.4	89.9	96.4	97.0	96.9
4.9	0.8	1.9	53.8	88.3	95.9	96.6	96.6
5	0.8	1.6	49.3	86.3	95.3	96.2	96.2
5.1	0.8	1.5	44.4	84.4	94.6	95.9	95.9
5.2	0.8	1.4	39.9	82.1	93.9	95.4	95.4
5.3	0.8	1.3	35.5	79.8	93.2	94.9	95.1
5.4	0.8	1.3	31.0	77.3	92.2	94.4	94.7
5.5	0.8	1.3	27.3	74.5	91.3	93.9	94.3
5.6	0.8	1.3	23.1	71.6	90.3	93.2	93.7
5.7	0.8	1.3	19.5	68.5	89.2	92.6	93.2
5.8	0.8	1.3	16.1	65.3	87.9	91.9	92.6
5.9	0.8	1.3	13.1	61.9	86.6	91.1	92.0
6	0.8	1.3	10.7	58.4	85.1	90.2	91.4
6.1	0.8	1.3	8.8	54.8	83.5	89.3	90.8
6.2	0.8	1.3	6.8	51.2	81.9	88.3	90.0
6.3	0.8	1.3	5.5	47.5	80.2	87.4	89.2
6.4	0.8	1.3	4.5	44.1	78.2	86.2	88.4
6.5	0.8	1.3	3.7	40.4	76.2	85.0	87.5
6.6	0.8	1.3	3.1	36.6	74.1	83.7	86.6
6.7	0.8	1.3	2.8	33.0	71.8	82.5	85.6
6.8	0.8	1.3	2.5	29.5	69.4	81.0	84.6
6.9	0.8	1.3	2.4	26.4	67.1	79.5	83.4
7	0.8	1.3	2.3	23.1	64.6	77.9	82.3

7.1	0.8	1.3	2.2	20.2	61.9	76.2	81.1
7.2	0.8	1.2	2.2	17.5	59.1	74.3	79.7
7.3	0.8	1.3	2.2	14.9	56.2	72.5	78.4
7.4	0.8	1.2	2.2	12.9	53.5	70.6	77.0
7.5	0.8	1.2	2.2	10.9	50.6	68.6	75.5
7.6	0.8	1.2	2.2	9.3	47.5	66.4	73.8
7.7	0.8	1.2	2.2	7.9	44.4	64.0	72.3
7.8	0.8	1.2	2.1	6.8	41.6	61.8	70.5
7.9	0.8	1.2	2.1	5.9	38.7	59.5	68.7
8	0.7	1.2	2.1	5.1	35.7	57.0	66.9
8.1	0.7	1.2	2.1	4.6	32.9	54.5	64.9
8.2	0.7	1.2	2.1	4.2	30.3	52.2	62.8
8.3	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.9	27.5	49.6	60.8
8.4	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.7	25.2	47.0	58.6
8.5	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.5	22.8	44.3	56.3
8.6	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.5	20.3	41.6	54.2
8.7	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.4	18.2	39.1	52.0
8.8	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.4	16.2	36.6	49.7
8.9	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.4	14.4	33.8	47.3
9	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.3	12.9	31.3	44.9
9.1	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.3	11.5	28.8	42.4
9.2	0.7	1.2	2.1	3.3	10.2	26.5	40.1
9.3	0.7	1.1	2.1	3.3	9.1	24.2	37.7
9.4	0.7	1.1	2.1	3.3	8.1	22.1	35.4
9.5	0.7	1.1	2.0	3.3	7.4	20.1	33.2
9.6	0.7	1.1	2.0	3.3	6.7	18.2	31.0
9.7	0.7	1.1	2.0	3.3	6.2	16.3	28.7
9.8	0.7	1.1	2.0	3.3	5.8	14.8	26.7
9.9	0.7	1.1	2.0	3.2	5.5	13.3	24.7
10	0.7	1.1	2.0	3.2	5.3	12.1	22.8
10.1	0.7	1.1	2.0	3.2	5.1	10.9	21.0
10.2	0.6	1.1	2.0	3.2	5.0	9.9	19.3
10.3	0.6	1.1	2.0	3.2	4.9	9.0	17.7
10.4	0.6	1.1	2.0	3.2	4.8	8.2	16.3
10.5	0.6	1.1	2.0	3.2	4.8	7.7	15.0
10.6	0.6	1.0	2.0	3.2	4.7	7.2	13.8
10.7	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.2	4.7	6.8	12.7
10.8	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.2	4.7	6.5	11.7
10.9	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.2	4.7	6.2	10.9
11	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.2	4.7	6.1	10.2
11.1	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.2	4.7	5.9	9.5
11.2	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.2	4.6	5.8	9.0

11.3	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.2	4.6	5.7	8.5
11.4	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.1	4.6	5.7	8.2
11.5	0.6	1.0	1.9	3.1	4.6	5.6	7.9
11.6	0.6	1.0	1.8	3.1	4.6	5.6	7.7
11.7	0.6	1.0	1.8	3.1	4.6	5.6	7.5
11.8	0.6	1.0	1.8	3.1	4.6	5.5	7.3
11.9	0.6	1.0	1.8	3.0	4.6	5.5	7.2
12	0.6	1.0	1.8	3.0	4.6	5.5	7.2
12.1	0.6	1.0	1.8	3.0	4.6	5.5	7.1
12.2	0.6	1.0	1.8	3.0	4.6	5.5	7.1
12.3	0.6	0.9	1.8	3.0	4.6	5.5	7.0
12.4	0.6	0.9	1.8	3.0	4.5	5.5	7.0
12.5	0.6	0.9	1.8	2.9	4.5	5.5	7.0
12.6	0.6	0.9	1.7	2.9	4.5	5.4	7.0
12.7	0.6	0.9	1.7	2.9	4.5	5.4	6.9
12.8	0.6	0.9	1.7	2.9	4.5	5.4	6.9
12.9	0.5	0.9	1.7	2.9	4.5	5.4	6.9
13	0.5	0.9	1.7	2.9	4.4	5.4	6.9
13.1	0.5	0.9	1.7	2.9	4.4	5.4	6.9
13.2	0.5	0.9	1.7	2.8	4.4	5.4	6.9
13.3	0.5	0.9	1.7	2.8	4.4	5.4	6.9
13.4	0.5	0.9	1.7	2.8	4.4	5.4	6.9
13.5	0.5	0.9	1.6	2.8	4.3	5.3	6.8
13.6	0.5	0.9	1.6	2.8	4.3	5.3	6.8
13.7	0.5	0.9	1.6	2.8	4.3	5.3	6.8
13.8	0.5	0.9	1.6	2.8	4.3	5.3	6.8
13.9	0.5	0.9	1.6	2.7	4.2	5.2	6.8
14	0.5	0.9	1.6	2.7	4.2	5.2	6.8
14.1	0.5	0.8	1.6	2.7	4.2	5.2	6.7
14.2	0.5	0.8	1.6	2.7	4.2	5.2	6.7
14.3	0.5	0.8	1.6	2.7	4.1	5.1	6.7

Graph # 1 The PDD curve is typically plotted with the depth in centimeter (cm) along the horizontal axis and the percentage dose along the vertical axis. It illustrates the relationship between the depth of the body tissues and the percentage of the maximum dose delivered at each depth.

The graph of the Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curve as a function of depth provides a visual representation of how the dose delivered by an electron beam changes as it penetrates into the body.

The electron energy determines the depth of penetration of the electrons into the tissue, and this depth influences the shape of the PDD curve.

The PDD% generally starts at 100% at the surface (depth of zero) and decreases as the depth increases. This decrease is due to the energy loss of the electron beam as it travels through the tissue.

The depth to which the electrons can penetrate the tissue is determined by their initial energy. Higher energy electrons can penetrate deeper into the tissue compared to lower energy ones. As you can see from the graph that the beam of the energy 6MeV deliver its maximum dose at the depth of 1.4cm and the beam of 22MeV energy, deliver its maximum 100% dose at the depth of 2.2cm.

Table 3 Depth VS Field sizes (energy=16MeV; SSD=100cm)

Percentage Depth Doses						
16 MeV electrons						
SSD=100cm						
Field Size	6x6cm ²	10x10cm ²	10x6cm ²	15x15cm ²	20x20cm ²	25x25cm ²
Depth [cm]	PDD%					
0	91.8	91.4	91.7	91.0	91.4	91.6
0.1	92.4	92.0	92.2	91.6	92.0	92.1
0.2	93.2	92.8	93.0	92.4	92.8	92.8
0.3	94.1	93.7	94.0	93.3	93.7	93.7
0.4	95.0	94.5	94.8	94.2	94.6	94.6
0.5	95.6	95.2	95.5	94.9	95.3	95.1
0.6	96.2	95.8	96.0	95.4	95.7	95.7
0.7	96.7	96.2	96.4	95.9	96.1	96.1
0.8	97.0	96.6	96.8	96.3	96.6	96.5
0.9	97.3	96.9	97.2	96.6	96.9	96.8
1	97.6	97.2	97.4	96.9	97.2	97.2
1.1	97.9	97.5	97.7	97.2	97.5	97.4
1.2	98.1	97.7	97.9	97.4	97.8	97.7
1.3	98.3	97.9	98.2	97.7	97.9	97.9
1.4	98.6	98.1	98.4	97.9	98.2	98.1
1.5	98.7	98.3	98.6	98.1	98.4	98.3
1.6	98.9	98.5	98.7	98.3	98.5	98.5
1.7	99.1	98.7	98.9	98.5	98.7	98.6
1.8	99.2	98.8	99.0	98.6	98.9	98.8
1.9	99.4	98.9	99.2	98.8	99.0	99.0
2	99.5	99.1	99.3	99.0	99.1	99.1
2.1	99.6	99.2	99.4	99.1	99.3	99.2
2.2	99.7	99.3	99.6	99.3	99.4	99.3
2.3	99.8	99.4	99.7	99.4	99.5	99.5
2.4	99.9	99.5	99.7	99.5	99.6	99.6
2.5	99.9	99.6	99.8	99.6	99.7	99.7
2.6	100.0	99.7	99.9	99.7	99.8	99.8
2.7	100.0	99.8	99.9	99.8	99.9	99.8
2.8	100.0	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
2.9	100.0	99.9	99.9	99.9	100.0	99.9
3	99.9	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
3.1	99.8	100.0	99.9	100.0	100.0	100.0
3.2	99.7	100.0	99.8	100.0	100.0	100.0
3.3	99.6	99.9	99.7	100.0	99.9	100.0
3.4	99.4	99.9	99.7	100.0	99.9	99.9

3.5	99.1	99.9	99.5	99.9	99.8	99.8
3.6	98.8	99.7	99.3	99.8	99.6	99.7
3.7	98.5	99.5	99.1	99.6	99.5	99.6
3.8	98.2	99.4	98.8	99.4	99.3	99.3
3.9	97.6	99.1	98.4	99.1	99.0	99.0
4	97.2	98.7	98.0	98.8	98.7	98.8
4.1	96.6	98.4	97.5	98.4	98.4	98.4
4.2	95.9	98.0	97.0	98.0	97.9	97.9
4.3	95.1	97.4	96.4	97.5	97.3	97.5
4.4	94.2	96.7	95.6	96.8	96.7	96.8
4.5	93.2	96.1	94.8	96.2	96.0	96.0
4.6	92.2	95.2	93.9	95.3	95.1	95.3
4.7	91.0	94.3	92.9	94.4	94.2	94.4
4.8	89.8	93.2	91.6	93.4	93.2	93.5
4.9	88.3	92.0	90.6	92.2	92.0	92.3
5	86.9	90.6	89.1	90.8	90.6	91.0
5.1	85.3	89.3	87.6	89.4	89.3	89.6
5.2	83.6	87.7	86.1	87.8	87.7	87.9
5.3	81.7	86.0	84.2	85.9	86.0	86.4
5.4	79.8	84.2	82.2	84.3	84.2	84.4
5.5	77.7	82.0	80.1	82.0	82.2	82.5
5.6	75.5	79.9	77.9	79.8	80.1	80.3
5.7	73.1	77.6	75.6	77.5	77.8	78.0
5.8	70.7	75.0	73.0	75.1	75.1	75.4
5.9	68.1	72.4	70.5	72.4	72.6	72.9
6	65.3	69.5	67.7	69.4	69.8	69.9
6.1	62.7	66.5	64.7	66.6	66.9	67.1
6.2	59.8	63.4	61.7	63.6	63.7	64.0
6.3	56.8	60.3	58.5	60.5	60.7	61.0
6.4	53.8	57.1	55.3	57.0	57.5	57.7
6.5	50.9	53.7	52.2	53.9	54.1	54.4
6.6	47.5	50.2	48.7	50.1	50.6	50.8
6.7	44.4	46.9	45.4	47.0	47.3	47.6
6.8	41.1	43.4	42.0	43.5	43.9	44.3
6.9	38.1	39.9	38.7	40.1	40.4	40.7
7	34.6	36.5	35.3	36.7	37.0	37.4
7.1	31.8	33.2	31.8	33.4	33.5	34.0
7.2	28.6	29.9	28.7	29.9	30.3	30.7
7.3	25.7	26.8	25.5	26.9	27.2	27.6
7.4	23.0	23.9	22.9	24.0	24.2	24.7
7.5	20.3	21.1	20.1	21.2	21.3	21.6
7.6	17.8	18.3	17.5	18.6	18.7	19.0

7.7	15.5	16.0	15.1	16.2	16.2	16.6
7.8	13.5	13.9	13.1	14.1	14.1	14.5
7.9	11.6	12.0	11.3	12.1	12.2	12.5
8	10.0	10.3	9.7	10.4	10.5	10.7
8.1	8.6	8.8	8.4	8.8	8.9	9.1
8.2	7.3	7.6	7.3	7.7	7.7	8.0
8.3	6.5	6.7	6.3	6.7	6.7	6.9
8.4	5.6	5.9	5.6	5.9	5.9	6.1
8.5	5.0	5.2	5.0	5.3	5.2	5.4
8.6	4.5	4.7	4.6	4.8	4.7	4.9
8.7	4.2	4.4	4.3	4.4	4.4	4.6
8.8	4.0	4.2	4.0	4.2	4.1	4.3
8.9	3.8	4.0	3.9	4.0	4.0	4.1
9	3.7	3.9	3.7	3.9	3.8	4.0
9.1	3.6	3.8	3.7	3.8	3.7	3.9
9.2	3.5	3.7	3.6	3.8	3.7	3.8
9.3	3.5	3.7	3.6	3.7	3.6	3.8
9.4	3.4	3.7	3.6	3.7	3.6	3.8
9.5	3.4	3.6	3.6	3.7	3.6	3.8
9.6	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7	3.6	3.8
9.7	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7	3.6	3.8
9.8	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7	3.6	3.7
9.9	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7	3.6	3.7
10	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.1	3.3	3.6	3.5	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.2	3.3	3.6	3.5	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.3	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.4	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.5	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.6	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.7	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.8	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7
10.9	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7
11	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7
11.1	3.2	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.5	3.7
11.2	3.2	3.5	3.4	3.5	3.5	3.6
11.3	3.2	3.5	3.4	3.5	3.5	3.6
11.4	3.2	3.5	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.6
11.5	3.2	3.5	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.6
11.6	3.2	3.4	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.6
11.7	3.2	3.4	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.6
11.8	3.1	3.4	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6

11.9	3.1	3.4	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.6
12	3.1	3.4	3.3	3.4	3.4	3.6
12.1	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.4	3.4	3.5
12.2	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.4	3.4	3.5
12.3	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.4	3.3	3.5
12.4	3.0	3.3	3.2	3.4	3.3	3.5
12.5	3.0	3.3	3.1	3.4	3.3	3.5
12.6	3.0	3.3	3.1	3.3	3.3	3.5
12.7	3.0	3.2	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.5
12.8	3.0	3.2	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.4
12.9	2.9	3.2	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.4
13	2.9	3.2	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.4
13.1	2.9	3.2	3.0	3.2	3.2	3.4
13.2	2.9	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.2	3.4
13.3	2.9	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.2	3.3
13.4	2.8	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.1	3.3
13.5	2.8	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.1	3.3
13.6	2.8	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.1	3.3
13.7	2.8	3.0	2.9	3.1	3.1	3.3
13.8	2.8	3.0	2.9	3.1	3.1	3.3
13.9	2.8	3.0	2.9	3.1	3.1	3.3
14	2.7	3.0	2.9	3.1	3.1	3.3
14.1	2.7	3.0	2.9	3.1	3.0	3.2
14.2	2.7	3.0	2.9	3.1	3.0	3.2
14.3	2.7	2.9	2.8	3.0	3.0	3.2
14.4	2.7	2.9	2.8	3.0	3.0	3.2
14.5	2.6	2.9	2.8	3.0	2.9	3.2
14.6	2.6	2.9	2.8	3.0	2.9	3.1
14.7	2.6	2.9	2.8	3.0	2.9	3.1
14.8	2.6	2.9	2.7	3.0	2.9	3.1
14.9	2.6	2.8	2.7	3.0	2.9	3.1
15	2.6	2.8	2.7	2.9	2.9	3.1
15.1	2.6	2.8	2.7	2.9	2.9	3.1
15.2	2.6	2.8	2.7	2.9	2.9	3.1
15.3	2.5	2.8	2.7	2.9	2.8	3.0
15.4	2.5	2.8	2.7	2.9	2.8	3.0
15.5	2.5	2.7	2.6	2.9	2.8	3.0
15.6	2.5	2.7	2.6	2.8	2.8	3.0
15.7	2.5	2.7	2.6	2.8	2.8	3.0
15.8	2.5	2.7	2.6	2.8	2.7	3.0
15.9	2.4	2.7	2.6	2.8	2.7	2.9
16	2.4	2.7	2.6	2.8	2.7	2.9

16.1	2.4	2.7	2.6	2.8	2.7	2.9
16.2	2.4	2.7	2.5	2.7	2.7	2.9
16.3	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.7	2.7	2.9
16.4	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.7	2.7	2.9
16.5	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.7	2.7	2.9
16.6	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.7	2.7	2.8
16.7	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.7	2.6	2.8
16.8	2.3	2.5	2.5	2.7	2.6	2.8
16.9	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.7	2.6	2.8
17	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.6	2.6	2.8
17.1	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.6	2.6	2.8
17.2	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.6	2.6	2.8
17.3	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.8
17.4	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.7
17.5	2.3	2.4	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.7
17.6	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.6	2.5	2.7
17.7	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.5	2.7
17.8	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.5	2.7
17.9	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.5	2.7
18	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.7
18.1	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.7
18.2	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.6
18.3	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.6
18.4	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.6
18.5	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.6
18.6	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.6
18.7	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.6
18.8	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.6
18.9	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5
19	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5
19.1	2.1	2.2	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.5
19.2	2.1	2.2	2.2	2.3	2.3	2.5
19.3	2.0	2.3	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.5
19.4	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.5
19.5	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.5
19.6	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.5
19.7	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.5
19.8	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.3	2.2	2.4

Graph# 2 The Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curve in relation to field size describes how the dose distribution of an electron beam changes with varying sizes of the treatment field.

The Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curve is influenced by the field size, which refers to the dimensions of the area being irradiated by the electron beam. The field size plays a role in shaping the dose distribution within the body.

The buildup region and the region where the maximum dose is delivered (d max) are primarily influenced by the energy of the electron beam rather than the field size.

The region, where the dose gradually decreases beyond the depth of the maximum dose (d max), can be affected by the field size. As the field size increases, the width of the fall-off generally broadens.

Photon Beam:

Table # 4 Depth VS Field sizes (constant energy=6MeV)

Percentage Depth Doses									
SSD 50cm									
Energy 6MeV									
Field size (cm)	4*4	5*5	6*6	7*7	8*8	10*10	12*12	15*15	20*20
Depth (cm)	PDD%								
0	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
1	93.9	95.4	96.5	97.3	97.9	98.9	99.7	100.6	101.4
2	84.6	86.7	88.3	89.7	90.7	92.6	94.1	95.6	96.8
3	73.7	76.4	78.8	80.8	82.4	85.1	87.3	89.5	92.3
4	63.1	66.2	69	71.4	73.4	76.7	79.4	82.1	85.7
5	54.2	57.3	60.1	62.6	64.8	68.4	71.3	74.5	78.3
6	46.3	49.3	52	54.5	56.8	60.6	63.6	67	71.3
7	39.3	42.2	44.9	47.4	49.7	53.6	56.6	60.1	64.2
8	33.4	36.2	38.7	41.1	43.4	47.2	50.2	53.7	57.9
9	28.5	31	33.4	35.7	37.8	41.5	44.5	47.9	52
10	24.3	26.7	28.7	30.8	32.8	36.3	39.2	42.6	46.7
11	20.7	22.7	24.7	26.6	28.5	31.7	34.4	37.7	41.7
12	17.6	19.4	21.2	23	24.8	27.7	30.3	33.3	37.2
13	15.1	16.7	18.2	19.9	21.5	24.2	26.5	29.4	33.1
14	12.9	14.3	15.7	17.2	18.6	21.1	23.2	25.9	29.4
15	11	12.2	13.5	14.8	16.1	18.4	20.3	22.9	26.2
16	9.4	10.5	11.6	12.8	13.9	16	18	20.2	23.2
17	8	9	10	11.1	12	13.9	15.6	17.8	20.7
18	6.8	7.7	8.6	9.6	10.4	12.2	13.7	15.7	18.5
19	5.8	6.6	7.4	8.3	9	10.7	12.2	13.9	16.4
20	4.9	5.6	6.3	7	7.8	9.4	10.7	12.3	14.5

Graph #3 The PDD (Percentage Depth Dose) curve is a graphical representation of the dose distribution of a photon beam as a function of depth in a medium. It describes how the dose delivered by the photon beam changes as it penetrates into the patient's tissue.

When the energy of a photon beam is constant, but the field size is varying, the shape of the Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curves will be influenced by the changing field size. By increasing the field size the PDD will increase and by decreasing the field size the PDD will also decrease.

Table # 5
Depth vs. Different Energies

Energy	6MV	10MV	15MV
Depth(cm)	PDD (%)		
0	52.1	40.9	36
1	97.6	91.4	85.2
2	98.7	100	98.6
3	94.9	98.5	99.7
4	90.7	94.7	97.3
5	86.6	90.9	93.6
6	82.5	87.2	89.8
7	78.5	83.3	86.4
8	74.9	79.8	82.8
9	70.8	76.2	79.4
10	67.3	72.8	76
11	64	69.6	73.2
12	60.4	66.4	70
13	57.5	63.5	66.9
14	54.5	60.6	64
15	51.6	57.9	61.3
16	49	55.1	58.7
17	46.3	52.7	56.4
18	44	50.4	53.9
19	41.7	48	51.6
20	39.5	45.8	49.5
21	37.4	43.7	47.4
22	35.5	41.7	45.3
23	33.7	39.9	43.5
24	31.9	38	41.7
25	30.3	36.3	39.9
26	28.7	34.6	38.3
27	27.3	33.2	36.7
28	25.9	31.6	35.1

Graph# 4 The PDD (Percentage Depth Dose) curve is a graphical representation of the dose distribution of a photon beam as a function of depth in a medium.

When the field size of a photon beam is kept constant, but the energy of the beam is varied, the shape and characteristics of the Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curves will primarily be influenced by the changing beam energy.

As the energy of the photon beam increases, the PDD will also increase.

Neutron Beam:

Table # 6 Depth VS Field sizes (to observe PDD)

Field size	5*5	10*10	15*15
Depth(cm)	PDD%		
0.5	100	100	100
2	90.8	93	93.3
3	85.2	87.6	88.4
4	78.8	82.5	83.6
5	72.7	77.3	79.2
6	67.2	71.8	74.5
7	61.7	66.7	70.2
8	56.2	61.6	65.6
9	51.7	56.8	61.7
10	46.7	52	57.5
12	38.4	44.5	49.2
14	31.6	37.2	41.2
16	25.7	31	33.5
18	20.7	26.5	29
20	16.8	22	24.7

Graph# 5 Fast neutron PDD (Percentage Depth Dose) curves represent the dose distribution of a fast neutron beam as a function of depth in a body.

The percentage depth dose (PDD) of a neutron beam depends on several factors, including the energy of the beam, field size etc. The PDD of a neutron beam decreases with increasing depth in tissue and increases with increasing field size.

3.1 Treatment Planning:

In this treatment planning we used data of 10 patients (6 females & 4 males) taken from hospital (SKMCH & RC), independent of time for their treatment. These patients had cancer at pelvic. The OARs nearer to the pelvic are rectum, bladder, small bowel, LT femoral head, RT femoral head and sigmoid colon.

Each patient has high energy radiations about 6 MV during their treatment.

In this treatment plan; IMRT planning developments and optimizations were performed using Varian 120-MLC (60 each side).

LINAC A high energy electron beam 6 MV is used in equally spaced 7 fields (3D). Optimization of beam intensity profile for each beam used to simulate by the (Varian 120-MLC LINAC) sliding window delivery technique. Different PTVs with different dose per fractions and different total number of fractions are delivered to the different patients. SIB-IMRT technique is used to deliver these

PTVs (66Gy, 60Gy, 59.4 and 54Gy) to the target volume.

3.2 Data Evaluation:

The pelvic part of body is used as a target volume for female patient and male patient with three different PTVs plan and having different dose per fractions. There is a lot of models to analyze the data in radio biology.

The one of the key tools to analyze the data in radiation biology is linear quadratic model. It provides a simple relationship between cell survival and delivered dose. The LQ model is mainly used to estimate equivalent radiotherapy schedules (e.g., calculate the equivalent dose in 2 Gy per fractions, EQD2).

α/β ratio is normally selected with its general values of acute late-responding tissues/organs which can be tumors or not. Generally, $\alpha/\beta = 10$ is used for acute responding tissues/organs and $\alpha/\beta = 3$ is used for late responding tissues/organs. Early responding tissues/organs are mostly accelerated tumors and late responding response comes from normal tissues.

Total Dose(D) (Gy)	Dose/Fractions (d)	No. of Fractions(n)
66.00	2.0	33
60.00	2.0	30
59.40	1.8	33
54.00	1.8	30

ORGAN at Risk:

The target volume in this treatment is pelvic organ. The defining OARs are listed below in table.

Table 7: List of OARs nearer to pelvic

OARs
Rectum
Lungs
Liver
Breast
Thyroid
Colon

Clinically each organ has different ability (depend on its functionality) to absorb radiation doses.

Table 8: Standard Values of α/β for OARs

OARs	α/β ratios for OARs (standard values)(reference)
Rectum	5
Lungs	2
Liver	3
Colon	6

We analyze the data at high radiation doses that is 6 MV with same PTVs (66Gy, 60Gy, 59.4Gy,54Gy). The aim of this study is to estimate that by giving two high radiations doses to the patients what will be the effect on surrounding tissues/cells nearer to the target volume.

Results:

For analysis of whole data using md+ calc. calculator which is based on LQ model. The target volume is pelvic. The α/β ratios values are 3, 10 for PTVs plans for pelvic at different dose per fraction for 6MV radiation energy. In below table it is a comparative reading for all PTVs (66,60,59.4,54). It shows the biological effect of dose on different radiations energies. The following prescribed PTVs shows different values of biological effective dose (BED), and equivalent dose per fraction 2(EQD2). For late responding tissues α/β ratio is 3 while for early responding tissue has value 10.

Table 9: α/β , BED and EQD for different PTV'S

Radiation energy (MV)	Total Dose(D) (Gray)	Dose /Fractions (d)	No.of Fractions(n)	α/β (Late response tissues)	BED (Gray)	EQD2	α/β (Acute response tissues)	BED	EQD2
6	66.00	2.0	33	3	110.00	66.00	10	79.20	66.00
6	60.00	2.0	30	3	96.00	57.60	10	72.00	60.00
6	59.40	1.8	33	3	95.04	57.02	10	70.09	58.41
6	54.00	1.8	30	3	86.40	51.84	10	63.72	53.10

Early and late effects of dose

It can be seen that the treatment for 54.9 Gy has less toxicity to normal tissue when compared to the overall dose of 60 Gy. 54 Gy demonstrates that the tumor's exposure to radiation is also significantly reduced.

3.3 TABLES for Defining OARs:

The below tables demonstrate the effect of high radiations used in treatment to diagnosis the damage of surrounding tissues. The table is for PTV 66Gy with 2 dose per fraction.

Table 10: BED & EQD2 for PTV-66 Gy

<i>Defining OARs</i>	α/β	<i>Dose per fraction (d/f Gy)</i>	<i>Radiation energy (MV)</i>	<i>BED (Gy)</i>	<i>EQD2 (Gy)</i>	<i>BED at ICRP</i>
<i>Lungs</i>	3	2	6	110	66.265	195
<i>Liver</i>	3.9	2	6	99.85	66.125	250
<i>Breast</i>	4	2	6	99.00	66	90
<i>Colon</i>	6	2	6	88	66.165	230

TABLES for Defining OARs:

The below tables demonstrate the effect of high radiations used in treatment to diagnosis the damage of surrounding tissues. The table is for PTV 60Gy with 2 dose per fraction.

Table 11: BED & EQD2 for PTV-60 Gy

Defining OARs	α/β	Dose per fraction (d/f Gy)	Radiation energy (MV)	BED (Gy)	EQD2 (Gy)	BED at ICRP
Lungs	3	2	6	100	60.240	195
Liver	3.9	2	6	90.77	60.112	250
Breast	4	2	6	90	60	90
Colon	6	2	6	80	60.150	230

TABLES for Defining OARs:

The below tables demonstrate the effect of high radiations used in treatment to diagnosis the damage of surrounding tissues. The table is for PTV 59.4Gy with 1.8 dose per fraction.

Table 12: BED & EQD2 values for PTV- 59.4 Gy

Defining OARs	α/β	Dose per fraction (d/f Gy)	Radiation energy (MV)	BED (Gy)	EQD2 (Gy)	BED at ICRP
Lungs	3	1.8	6	95.04	57.25	195
Liver	3.9	1.8	6	86.82	57.49	250
Breast	4	1.8	6	86.13	57.52	90
Colon	6	1.8	6	77.22	58.06	230

TABLES for Defining OARs:

The below tables demonstrate the effect of high radiations used in treatment to diagnosis the damage of surrounding tissues. The table is for PTV 54Gy with 1.8 dose per fraction.

Table 13: BED & EQD2 values for PTV- 54 Gy

Defining OARs	α/β	Dose per fraction (d/f Gy)	Radiation energy (MV)	BED (Gy)	EQD2 (Gy)	BED at ICRP
Lungs	3	1.8	6	86.4	52.04	195
Liver	3.9	1.8	6	78.92	52.26	250
Breast	4	1.8	6	78.30	52.28	90
Colon	6	1.8	6	70.20	52.78	230

3.4 Discussion

A visual illustration of how the dosage produced by an electron beam changes as it penetrates into the body is provided by the graph of the Percentage Depth dosage (PDD) curve as a function of depth as shown in graph 1.

The PDD curve's shape is influenced by the depth to which electrons penetrate tissue, which is determined by their energy. At the shallowest depths near the surface, the PDD curve exhibits a region called the "buildup region." In this region, the dose initially increases rapidly as the electrons enter the medium and rapidly deposit their energy due to interactions with atomic electrons. The extent of the buildup region depends on the energy of the electron beam. Higher energy beams have a smaller buildup region since the electrons penetrate deeper into the medium before scattering significantly.

Conversely, lower energy beams have a larger buildup region due to more frequent interactions and scattering near the surface.

As depth increases, the PDD% typically drops from 100% at the surface (depth of zero). This decline is brought on by the electron beam's energy loss during passage through the tissue.

The starting energy of the electrons determines how far they can travel through the tissue. Compared to lower energy electrons, higher energy electrons can pierce deeper into the tissue. The graph shows that the 6MeV beam's maximum dose is delivered at a depth of 1.4 cm, while the 22MeV beam's maximum 100% dose is delivered at a depth of 2.2 cm.

The PDD curve represents the dose distribution as a function of depth in tissue. When higher energy electrons are used, the PDD curve will show a more gradual decrease in dose as depth increases. This is because higher energy electrons can travel deeper into the tissue, resulting in a more uniform dose distribution throughout a larger region.

On the other hand, lower energy electrons have a shorter range and deposit most of their energy near the surface. Consequently, the PDD curve for lower energy electrons will exhibit a more rapid decrease in dose as depth increases. The dose delivered by lower energy electrons is mostly concentrated near the surface, making them suitable for treating superficial tumors.

In summary, the PDD curve graphically represents how the dose delivered by an electron beam changes as it travels into a medium. It provides valuable information for treatment planning in radiation therapy, ensuring that the prescribed dose is accurately delivered to the target while

minimizing the dose to surrounding healthy tissues.

The field size, which refers to the dimensions of the region being irradiated by the electron beam, has an impact on the Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curve. The distribution of the dose within the body is influenced by the field size as shown in graph 2.

The energy of the electron beam, as opposed to the field size, has a greater influence on the accumulation region and the area where the maximum dose is delivered (d_{max}).

The field size can have an impact on the area where the dose gradually declines after reaching the maximum dose depth (d_{max}). The fall-off width often widens as the size of the field grows. This widening of the region is due to increased electron scattering within the medium and the larger area over which the dose is distributed.

The increased field size leads to a more gradual dose falloff beyond the region where the maximum dose is delivered (d_{max}). The region where the dose decreases to a low level, remains relatively unaffected by the field size.

It's important to note that the field size influences the PDD curve at the region where the dose gradually starts decreasing beyond the d_{max} point. Therefore, when planning a radiation therapy treatment, the field size needs to be carefully considered to achieve the desired dose distribution and balance the treatment goals of delivering an appropriate dose to the target area while minimizing the dose to healthy tissues and organs at risk.

As shown in graph 3, the shape of the Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curves will be affected by the changing field size when the energy of a photon beam remains constant but the field size varies. The PDD will rise as the field size increases, and vice versa when the field size decreases.

With a larger field size, there is more lateral scattering and increased dose deposition in the surrounding tissue but with a smaller field size, there is less lateral scattering, resulting in a more focused and concentrated beam. Consequently, the dose drops more quickly with depth by using the smaller field size.

As seen in graph 4, when the field size of a photon beam is maintained while the beam energy is changed, the shape and characteristics of the Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curves will be mostly affected by the altered beam energy. The PDD will increase along with the photon beam's energy.

This is because higher-energy photons have a greater ability to penetrate tissues, resulting in a more focused dose distribution. Higher-energy photons can penetrate deeper into the tissue and deposit their energy at greater depths compared to lower-energy photons.

The PDD of a neutron beam decreases with increasing depth in tissue and increases with increasing field size. This is because larger field sizes result in a greater amount of scattering and a more uniform dose distribution, which can increase the PDD at the surface and decrease it at greater depths. The depth at which the PDD reaches a maximum value, known as the depth of dose maximum (DDM) can also vary depending on the energy and field size of the neutron beam. In general, higher energy and larger field size neutron beams will have a deeper DDM, while lower energy and smaller field size neutron beams will have a shallower DDM.

Understanding BED and EQD2 will be helpful for discussions. The biological dosage (BED) that is given to a tumor or organ is measured. The theoretical dose would result in the same biological endpoints as those under discussion if it were administered in infinitely small fractions. It enables the quantitative evaluation of the biological impacts linked to various radiation delivery patterns. The equivalent dose in 2-Gy fractions is known as EQD2. The 'gold standard' for external beam radiation was thought to be a fraction size of roughly 2 Gy.

Tables 10, 11, 12, 13 are showing the BED and EQD of the OARs. The value of BED for OARs is contrasted with the baseline ICRP value. BED of all OARs is in the acceptable range, although the BED of the breast at the PTV of 66 Gy is higher than its usual value. For the PTV of 66 Gy, radiation treatment planning should be revised; otherwise, this penetration of dose may result in serious harm to the breast.

3.5 Conclusion:

The analysis of the ionizing beam's depth dose characteristics contributes to improving the precision of radiation treatment planning. It should be noted that the energy of the ionizing beam is the key component of the absorption dose's distinctive features at a certain depth in the tissue or equivalent material. Although other dosimetric factors, such as field size and SSD, can also affect doses at specific regions, the spectrum and point-to-point distribution of the dosage is a unique characteristic of the beam energy. For radiotherapy, the beam should always be capable of giving the exact dose distribution that the target volume and its surrounding tissues require.

Percentage depth dose (PDD) describes the dose distribution of a radiation beam as it penetrates the patient's body. It depends on some factors such as field size, energy of the beam. For different Ionizing radiations beam's penetration in the tissues are calculated by PDD. The PDD curve graphically represents how the dose delivered by an ionizing beam changes as it travels into a medium. Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curves will be affected by the changing field size when the energy of a photon beam remains constant but the field size varies. The PDD will rise as the field size increases, and vice versa when the field size decreases.

BED and EQD are important concepts used to estimate the potential biological effects of ionizing radiation on living tissue. By using the concepts of biological and equivalent dose, radiation therapists can estimate the potential biological effects of radiation on a patient's tissue and adjust the treatment plan accordingly to ensure the best possible outcomes while minimizing the risk of side effects.

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